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Review Article

**RAPID DETECTION OF MILK ADULTERATION USING MID-
INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (MIRS): RECENT ADVANCES
AND APPLICATIONS**S Harish*, K. Navyaja², M. Gurava Reddy³, Dr. K. Venu Gopal⁴.¹B. Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.⁴Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.**Abstract:**

Milk adulteration poses significant health risks and economic consequences. Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy (MIRS) has emerged as a powerful tool for rapid and accurate detection of contaminants. Recent advances in MIRS technology enable simultaneous identification of multiple adulterants, including veterinary drugs, toxins, and chemical additives. This non-destructive method offers improved sensitivity, specificity, and speed compared to traditional detection methods. Quantitative analysis capabilities allow for precise monitoring and control. Portable MIRS devices and expanded spectral libraries enhance on-site analysis and contaminant identification. Integration with other technologies further strengthens detection capabilities. This review highlights MIRS applications in milk adulteration detection, emphasizing its potential to ensure dairy product quality and safety. The study demonstrates MIRS's efficacy in protecting consumers and promoting integrity in the dairy industry, underscoring its significance in food safety and quality control.

Keywords: Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy, Milk Adulteration, Quality Control, Rapid Detection, Food Safety.

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INTRODUCTION:

Milk is a fundamental component of the human diet, particularly for infants, children, and the elderly, due to its rich nutritional content. It serves as a primary source of essential nutrients such as proteins, calcium, vitamins, and fats. However, the safety and quality of milk have become major concerns globally due to the widespread adulteration practices and contamination issues that compromise its nutritional value and pose significant health risks to consumers. Milk adulteration refers to the intentional addition of substances such as water, starch, detergents, urea, and other low-cost materials to increase the volume and profit margin, often at the expense of its quality and safety. Contaminants, on the other hand, may enter milk either through poor hygiene practices, environmental pollution, or the use of veterinary drugs, pesticides, and antibiotics in dairy farming.

Adulteration and contamination of milk can have severe health consequences. For example, the dilution of milk with water reduces its nutritional content, while the addition of substances like urea and starch can cause serious health problems, including kidney failure and digestive issues. The presence of contaminants such as antibiotics and pesticides, on the other hand, can lead to allergic reactions, antibiotic resistance, and long-term exposure to harmful chemicals. Given the widespread nature of these practices, particularly in regions with less stringent regulatory frameworks, there is an urgent need for effective methods to detect and quantify adulterants and contaminants in milk.

Traditional methods for detecting adulterants and contaminants in milk include chemical analysis, microbiological testing, and chromatographic techniques such as high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and gas chromatography (GC). While these methods are highly sensitive and accurate, they are often time-consuming, labor-intensive, and require sophisticated laboratory equipment. Furthermore, they involve the destruction of the sample and are not suitable for real-time monitoring. As a result, there is a growing demand for rapid, non-invasive, and cost-effective techniques that can detect adulterants and contaminants in milk while ensuring its quality and safety [1].

Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy in Determination of Milk Adulteration:

In recent years, MIR spectroscopy has gained significant attention as a powerful tool for the detection of milk adulterants and contaminants. MIR spectroscopy is based on the absorption of infrared

light by molecules, which causes molecular vibrations that are characteristic of specific functional groups. By analyzing the absorption spectra, it is possible to identify and quantify various components present in a sample. The MIR region ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is particularly useful for studying organic molecules because it contains absorption bands corresponding to key functional groups such as C-H, O-H, N-H, and C=O, which are commonly found in proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, and other biomolecules in milk.

One of the primary advantages of MIR spectroscopy is its ability to provide rapid, non-destructive analysis of complex matrices such as milk. Unlike traditional methods, which require extensive sample preparation, MIR spectroscopy can be applied directly to milk samples without the need for chemical reagents or elaborate preprocessing steps. This makes it an ideal technique for routine quality control in the dairy industry, where large volumes of milk need to be tested in a short period of time [2].

Recent Advances in MIR Spectroscopy for Milk Analysis

Recent advances in milk adulteration detection focus on enhancing accuracy, speed, and sensitivity to detect even trace levels of contaminants. Here are some notable developments:

1. Spectroscopic Technique
2. Portable and Handheld devices
3. Biosensors and immunoassays
4. Machine Learning and Chemometrics
5. DNA- Based methods
6. Nanosensors and Nanotechnology

1. Spectroscopic Techniques

A spectroscopic technique is a method used to study the interaction between matter and electromagnetic radiation (light). It involves measuring the absorption, emission, or scattering of light (or other electromagnetic waves) by atoms, molecules, or materials to gain insights into their physical, chemical, and structural properties.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR has improved sensitivity for detecting multiple adulterants simultaneously. It's faster and more precise than traditional MIR and is commonly used in conjunction with machine learning for complex analysis.

Raman spectroscopy

Raman provides a complementary method to IR techniques, offering specific insights into protein and fat content. Advances allow it to detect lower levels of contaminants like melamine and antibiotics [3]. Fig.1.

Represents that “Raman Spectroscopy” in the detection of urea adulteration in milk

Fig.1 Raman Spectroscopy in the detection of urea adulteration in milk.

2. Portable and Handheld Devices

Portable and handheld devices are compact, lightweight electronic gadgets designed for mobility and convenience. These devices are easy to carry and operate, making them highly functional for various personal, professional, and industrial applications. Fig.2. Represents the milktech apparatus in determination of milk added with reconstituting or high acidity.

1) Portable Spectrometers: Handheld MIR and NIR (Near-infrared) Spectrometers are now available, enabling on-site milk testing. Testing devices accessibility in rural or remote dairy farms, providing real-time adulteration detection without the need for lab facilities.

2) Micro liquid-based devices: These compact, lab-on-a-chip systems can detect multiple contaminants in small milk samples with high precision, making the ideal for point-of-use-testing [4]

Fig.2 Milktech apparatus in determination of milk added with reconstituting or high acidity.

Benefits of Machine Learning in Milk Adulteration Detection:

Speed: Enables rapid analysis of large datasets and real-time detection.

Accuracy: Machine learning models can detect adulterants at low concentrations, which may be difficult with traditional methods.

Scalability: Once trained, models can be applied to vast datasets, making them suitable for large-scale milk quality monitoring.

This procedure outlines the steps for using data processing and machine learning to detect and quantify adulterants in milk through spectroscopic analysis, ensuring quality control and food safety [5].

3. Biosensors and Immuno Assays

Biosensors are Analytical devices that combine a biological recognition element (e.g., enzymes, antibodies, or DNA) with a physical transducer to detect and measure specific substances, converting

biological signals into measurable electrical or optical signals.

Immunoassays are Biochemical tests that use the specific binding between an antigen and an antibody to detect or quantify substances, often applied in diagnostics, research, and environmental monitoring.

1) Electrochemical Biosensors: These sensors are increasingly used for their sensitivity and low detection limits, particularly for urea, formaldehyde, and antibiotics. Some sensors even employ nanomaterials (like graphene) for enhanced sensitivity.

2) Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay Innovations (ELISA): ELISA tests have been refined for faster detection of specific adulterants, including antibiotic residues, pesticides, and allergence, by targeting specific proteins or enzymes in milk [6]. Fig.3. is representing Graphene-based biosensors in milk analysis.

Fig.3 Graphene -based biosensors in milk analysis

4. Machine Learning and Chemometrics

Machine Learning is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on developing algorithms and statistical models that enable computers to learn and make decisions or predictions from data without being explicitly programmed.

Chemometrics is a field of chemistry that applies mathematical, statistical, and computational methods to analyze and interpret chemical data, often used for improving experimental design, identifying patterns, and developing predictive models.

1) Artificial intelligence (AI) For Data Analysis: AI and Machine Learning algorithms are employed to analyze complex spectral data from spectroscopy methods, improving detection accuracy and identifying patterns that indicate adulteration.

2) Chemometric Analysis: Statistical methods such as principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least squares (PLS) are used to interpret spectroscopic data, making it easier to distinguish between pure and adulterated milk [7]. Fig.4. represents the chemometrics for rapid and non-destructive determination of milk acidity and adulteration.

Fig.4. chemometrics for rapid and non-destructive determination of milk acidity and adulteration.

5. DNA-Based Methods

DNA-Based Method is an Analytical or diagnostic techniques that utilize DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid) sequences, structures, or properties to identify, detect, or analyze biological samples. These methods are commonly applied in molecular biology, genetics, forensic science, medicine, and environmental studies. Fig.5. is representing the process of identifying the authenticity of dairy products using PCR Technology.

DNA Barcoding and Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS): These methods help detect milk from non-declared animal species, verifying the milk's authenticity and preventing mislabeling.

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR): PCR-Based methods allow for the identification of specific contaminants or allergence in milk, inducing the presence of unwanted microbial DNA [8].

Fig.5. The process of identifying the authenticity of dairy products using PCR Technology.

6. Nanosensors and Nanotechnology

Nanosensors are Devices or systems that utilize nanoscale materials or components to detect physical, chemical, or biological changes with high sensitivity and specificity, often used in environmental monitoring, healthcare, and industrial applications.

Nanotechnology is a field of science and engineering focused on the design, manipulation, and application of materials and devices at the nanoscale (1 to 100 nanometers) to exploit unique physical, chemical, and biological properties. Fig.6. represents the Nanosensors platform for detection of milk adulterants.

Example for Nanosensors and Nano Technology:

Gold and Silver Nanoparticles: These nanoparticles are used in colorimetric assays, where color changes indicate the presence of adulterants like urea or

melamine. They offer high sensitivity and rapid results.

Magnetic Nanoparticles: Used in separation and purification steps, these nanoparticle help isolate contaminants, improving detection of minute amounts of adulterants.

These recent advances make milk adulteration detection faster, more reliable, and accessible, supporting the dairy industry's goal of ensuring milk quality and safety [8].

Fig.6. Nanosensors platforms for detection of mil adulterants.

Fundamental Principle of MIR

MIR spectroscopy operates in the spectral range of 2.5 to 25 μm (4000 to 400 cm^{-1}), which corresponds to the vibrational frequencies of molecular bonds such as C-H, O-H, and N-H. These bonds are present in many adulterants and contaminants, making MIR spectroscopy a powerful technique for detecting specific molecular signatures. The interaction of infrared light with milk samples causes molecular vibrations, which result in absorption patterns unique to different substances. By analyzing these absorption spectra, researchers can identify the presence and concentration of various adulterants and contaminants [9]. Fig.7. represents a detailed illustration of MIR Spectroscopy that interacting with sample.

Fig.7 A detailed illustration of MIR spectroscopy that interacting with sample.

MID-Infrared Spectroscopy (MIR) For Milk Analysis

Sample Preparation:

Collect a small volume (typically 1-2 mL) of milk sample. Filter the sample if necessary to remove any particulate matter or solids that could interfere with the measurement. Place the sample in a sample holder or cuvette designed for MIR spectroscopy.

Instrument Setup:

Infrared Light Source: The instrument uses a light source that emits mid-infrared radiation (wavelength range 2.5–25 μm).

Interferometer (for FTIR-based systems): The light is passed through an interferometer to generate an interference pattern, improving resolution.

Sample Compartment: The infrared light beam passes through the milk sample, where molecular bonds absorb specific frequencies of the IR light.

Measurement:

The MIR light interacts with the sample. Molecules in the milk absorb light at specific frequencies corresponding to the vibrational modes of bonds such as O-H, N-H, and C-H.

The amount of absorbed light is measured as a function of wavelength, creating an absorption spectrum.

Detection:

The light that is not absorbed by the sample reaches the detector. The detector measures the intensity of the transmitted light across various wavelengths [5].

Data Collection and Spectrum Generation:

The instrument records the absorbance (or transmittance) spectrum, which displays how much light is absorbed at each wavelength. Peaks in the absorption spectrum correspond to specific molecular vibrations and can be used to identify various components or adulterants in the milk.

Data Analysis:

Using software, analyze the absorption peaks. Each peak represents the vibrational frequency of specific molecular bonds in adulterants or contaminants (e.g., C-H, O-H, or N-H). Compare the sample spectrum to reference spectra of known milk components and potential adulterants or contaminants. [10]

Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis:

The area under the absorption peaks can be used to quantify the amount of a specific adulterant or contaminant. Chemometric models like partial least squares (PLS) or principal component analysis (PCA) can be applied for more complex samples, enabling simultaneous detection of multiple components.

Calibration and Validation:

Calibration curves are created by measuring known concentrations of potential adulterants or contaminants in milk samples. The instrument is regularly calibrated to ensure accuracy, and validation is done using control samples.

Interpretation:

Based on the spectral data and analysis, the presence of specific adulterants or contaminants in the milk is confirmed. The concentration levels of each component can be determined from the intensity of the corresponding peaks.

Reporting Results:

The final results, including qualitative detection and quantitative measurement of adulterants or contaminants, are compiled into a report for further action or quality assurance. This procedure allows for rapid, non-invasive detection of milk adulterants and contaminants with high accuracy using mid-infrared spectroscopy [10].

MIR Spectroscopy in Detection of Milk Adulterants**1. Detection of water content in milk sample**

Water is the most common adulterant added to milk to increase its volume. MIR spectroscopy has been used to detect the dilution of milk by water through the analysis of specific absorption bands related to water content. The strong O-H stretching vibration of water at around 3400 cm^{-1} can be quantified accurately,

making MIR an effective tool for detecting even small amounts of added water [11].

2. Detection of urea and starch

Urea is sometimes added to milk to artificially increase nitrogen content, simulating higher protein levels. Starch is also used as a thickening agent to mask the addition of water. Recent advancements in MIR spectroscopy allow for the detection of these adulterants by analyzing specific absorption bands corresponding to urea's C=O stretching (around 1600 cm^{-1}) and starch's C-H and O-H vibrations (around $1000\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) [12].

3. Detection of synthetic milk

Synthetic milk is a dangerous form of adulteration involving the use of synthetic chemicals to mimic the properties of real milk. The components of synthetic milk include detergents, oil, and caustic soda. MIR spectroscopy can identify the presence of these substances by detecting absorption bands associated with long-chain hydrocarbons, fatty acids, and other molecular components specific to synthetic milk formulations [13].

4. Detection of antibiotic residues

Antibiotics used in dairy farming can lead to residues in milk, which pose health risks such as allergic reactions and antibiotic resistance. MIR spectroscopy has shown great potential in detecting common antibiotics such as penicillin and tetracycline by targeting specific functional groups (e.g., amide bonds) in these molecules. Advanced chemometric models have been developed to differentiate between antibiotics and other milk components, enhancing the sensitivity of detection [14].

5. Detection of pesticides and heavy metals

Pesticides and heavy metals, such as lead and cadmium, are harmful contaminants that can enter milk through contaminated feed or water. MIR spectroscopy can detect the presence of these contaminants by identifying their characteristic vibrational modes. For example, the C-Cl and P=O bonds in organophosphates exhibit distinct absorption bands in the mid-infrared region, allowing for precise identification of these pesticide residues [15].

6. Multicomponent Analysis

One of the major advantages of MIR spectroscopy is its ability to perform multi-component analysis, meaning that multiple adulterants and contaminants can be detected simultaneously. This is achieved through advanced chemometric techniques such as partial least squares regression (PLS) and principal component analysis (PCA), which enable the extraction of relevant information from complex spectral data. These methods have significantly improved the accuracy and robustness of MIR-based milk analysis [16].

Common Milk Adulterants

S.NO	CATEGORY	COMPONENTS
1.	Shelf-life Enhancers	Salt, Boric Acid, Formalin, Salicylic Acid, H ₂ O ₂ .
2.	Neutralizers	Sodium Carbonate, Sodium Bicarbonate.
3.	Emulsifiers	Detergent, Surfactant, Soap.
4.	Fat Enhancers	Animal/vegetable oil.
5.	Nitrogen Enhancers	Urea, Melamine.
6.	Density Enhancers	Starch, Sugar.
7.	Diluents	Water, Milk whey.

Adulterants & Its Harmfull Effects

S.NO	ADULTERANTS	HARMFULL EFFECTS
1.	Urea	Kidney Stones
2.	Melamine	Renal Failure
3.	Formalin	Nausea, Abdominal Pain
4.	Starch	Diarrhea
5.	Carbonates, bi-carbonates	Hormone destruction
6.	Starch, solid milk paste	Stomach related problems

Maximum Limit of Mostly Used Adulterants and Contaminants

S.NO	ADULTERANT	OBJECTIVE	LIMIT
1.	Urea	To increase the non-protein nitrogen content of the milk	<70mg/100ml
2.	Melamine	To increase the protein content of the milk	2.5mg/kg for adults, 1mg for infants
3.	Ammonium Sulphate	To maintain the density of the diluted mil and increase the lactometer reading	0.79 per litre
4.	Detergent	To emulsify the non-dairy fat	5-10 ml of sample
5.	Vegetable Oil	To replace the actual milk fat	1/s teaspoon
6.	Formalin, Salicylic Acid, Benzoic Acid, Hydrogen peroxide	To increase the shelf-life of the prepared milk	0.5ml/kg

S.NO.	SAMPLE	ADULTERANTS	ANALYTICAL METHODS
1.	Buffalo milk	Water	Total reflection MID-Infrared spectroscopy (MIRS) and partial squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA)
2.	Cow milk	Sucrose	FTIR Spectroscopy
3.	Cow milk	Nitrogen rich compounds and urea	Attenuated total reflectance Fourier-transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) Spectroscopy.
4.	Milk matrices Liquid milk Milk powder	Melamine Melamine in milk matrixes including liquid milk. Melamine in milk powder.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FTIR Methods to detect 1ppm of melamine in infant formula powder • MIRs Technique. • (ATR-FTIR) in conjugation with single-clay soft independent modelling of class analogy (SIMCA).

5.	melamine	Sucrose, Soluble starch (amylose and amylopectin), sodium bicarbonate, hydrogen peroxide and formaldehyde.	Machine learning techniques.
6.	Low lactose milk	Lactose	FTIR with machine learning tools.
7.	Bovine milk samples	Aflatoxins	Principle component analysis (PCA)
8.	Milk samples	Gram- positive & Gram -negative bacteria	(ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy
9.	Milk samples	Microbial content	FTIR in combination with partial least square regression (PLSR)
10.	Cow milk	Antibiotics or antibiotic residues	Immune chemical methods with mass spectrometry
11.	Cow milk	Tetracycline antibiotics	MID-FTIR with chemometric analysis
12.	Fluid milk Powdered milk	Tylosin in fluid milk Tylosin in powdered milk	ATR-FTR Spectroscopy associated with multilayer perceptron network MLP and partial least squares (PLS). FTIR Spectroscopy in association with random forest.
13.	Cow's milk	Beta lactam –Antibiotics (penicillin & ampicillin)	Infrared and Raman spectra together with the density functional theory. (DFT) AND (PCA).
14.	Bovine milk	Lactoferrin	Mid infrared spectrometry (MIR)

Common Adulterants Detected by Portable MIR Spectroscopy:

Water: Detected by O-H stretching vibrations in the region $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Urea: Characterized by the N-H stretching vibrations around $\sim 3340\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Starch: Identified by peaks in the range of $1150\text{--}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

C=O stretching peaks around $\sim 1040\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Synthetic Milk Glucose: Detected by peaks corresponding to chemicals like detergents, caustic soda, and other synthetic components [17].

Applications of MID-Infrared Spectroscopy in Determination of Milk Adulterants and Contaminants

Mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy has emerged as a powerful analytical tool for detecting milk adulterants due to its ability to provide rapid, non-destructive, and comprehensive analysis [19]. Here are some key applications of MIR spectroscopy in determining milk adulterants:

1. Water Detection: Measures water content to identify adulteration with added water.

2. Urea Identification: Detects urea levels, which can indicate quality or adulteration.

3. Detergent Detection: Identifies residues from cleaning agents used in dairy processing.

4. Synthetic Milk Detection: Differentiates between genuine milk and synthetic alternatives through spectral analysis [14].

5. Component Quantification: Simultaneously quantifies fat, protein, and lactose levels to assess quality.

6. Detection of Added Substances: Identifies various substances like starch and glucose that may be added to milk.

7. Quality Control: Integrates into processing to monitor milk quality at various stages for compliance.

8. Milk Powder Characterization: Assesses quality and detects adulterants in milk powder.

9. Non-Destructive Testing: Allows repeated testing on the same sample without damage.

10. Real-Time Monitoring: Portable devices enable real-time quality and adulteration checks during transportation and storage [18].

These applications highlight the effectiveness of MIR spectroscopy in ensuring milk quality and safety.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, recent advances in mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy have significantly enhanced the

detection and determination of milk adulterants and contaminants, addressing critical concerns in food safety and quality assurance. The non-destructive nature of MIR, combined with its rapid analysis capabilities, makes it a valuable tool for the dairy industry. Technological improvements, such as enhanced sensitivity, portable devices, and the integration of machine learning, have further expanded the scope of MIR applications, enabling the simultaneous detection of multiple adulterants with high accuracy. The development of comprehensive spectral databases and standardized methodologies will facilitate widespread adoption of MIR spectroscopy in routine quality control processes. Moreover, real-time monitoring solutions can help identify adulteration during transportation and storage, ensuring the integrity of dairy products. As regulatory pressures increase and consumer awareness grows, the demand for reliable and efficient methods of detecting milk adulteration will continue to rise. Future research and technological advancements are expected to further refine MIR techniques, enhancing their applicability and reliability in the dairy sector. Ultimately, these developments will not only improve food safety but also foster consumer confidence in the quality of milk and dairy products.

Challenges and Limitations

1. Despite the many advancements in MIR spectroscopy for milk analysis, several challenges remain. The accuracy of MIR spectroscopy can be affected by the presence of overlapping absorption bands, particularly when multiple adulterants or contaminants are present in the milk sample. Calibration of spectrometers is also crucial for obtaining reliable results, and variations in milk composition due to geographical or seasonal factors can complicate spectral analysis. Furthermore, the high cost of some MIR instruments may limit their widespread adoption in lower-income regions [19].

Future Trends

The future of MIR spectroscopy in milk analysis looks promising with the continued development of more sensitive and affordable instruments. Integration with other spectroscopic techniques, such as near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, could enhance the detection capabilities by providing complementary information about molecular structures. Additionally, the increasing use of cloud-based data analysis platforms could facilitate real-time monitoring of milk quality across global supply chains, improving traceability and safety.

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